

1 Record sea surface temperature jump in
2 2023/24 unlikely but not unexpected

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18 **Global ocean surface temperatures were at record levels for more than a year since April 2023,**
19 **exceeding the previous record from 2015/16 by 0.25°C on average between April 2023 and**
20 **March 2024¹. The nearly global extent and unprecedented intensity of this event prompted**
21 **questions about how exceptional it was and whether climate models can represent such**
22 **record-shattering jumps in surface ocean temperatures². Here we construct observation-based**
23 **synthetic timeseries to show that a jump in global sea surface temperatures that breaks the**
24 **previous record by at least 0.25°C is a 1-in-512-year event under the current long-term warming**
25 **trend (1-in-205-year to 1-in-1,185-year event; 95% confidence interval). Without a global**
26 **warming trend, such an event would have been practically impossible. Using 270 simulations**
27 **from a wide range of fully coupled climate models, we show that these models successfully**
28 **simulate such record-shattering jumps in global ocean surface temperatures, underpinning the**
29 **models' usefulness in understanding characteristics, drivers, and consequences of such events.**
30 **These model simulations suggest that the record-shattering jump in surface ocean**
31 **temperatures in 2023/24 was an extreme event after which surface ocean temperatures are**
32 **expected to revert to the expected long-term warming trend.**

33

34 Since April 2023, global ocean (60°S-60°N; excluding cloudy and largely sea-ice covered polar
35 regions due to sparse data) surface temperatures have exceeded previous sea surface
36 temperature (SST) records by a large margin (Fig 1a). This record-breaking SST event is not only
37 a global record-breaking event but also unprecedented in the magnitude by which it surpassed
38 previous records. Over the summer of 2023, the margin by which SSTs exceeded the previous
39 record that occurred in 2015/2016 has grown to 0.2-0.3°C (Fig. 1a). Overall, the annually
40 averaged SSTs from April 2023 to March 2024 were 0.25°C larger based on NOAA OI SST V2.1¹
41 than the previous record SSTs when averaged over the same months of the year. This global
42 record-shattering jump in SSTs (“record-shattering jump” is here defined as a record-breaking
43 jump in annual (April to March) and globally averaged SSTs that exceeds previous records by at
44 least 0.25°C, as observed in 2023/24) coincides in time with record atmospheric surface
45 temperatures in late 2023³⁻⁶ and early 2024^{7,8}. Moreover, the record-shattering jump in SSTs is
46 believed to be responsible for the global atmospheric record surface warming^{5,6}, although
47 surface temperature extremes over land and ocean are not necessarily related^{9,10}. The record-
48 shattering jump in globally averaged SSTs has been a subject of high attention in the scientific
49 community^{11,12} and the general public^{13,14}. It has, for example, recently been argued that part of
50 the jump was caused by low albedo due to reduced low-cloud cover¹⁵. Since mid-July, globally
51 averaged SSTs are no longer record-breaking but remained still warmer than in any year before
52 the jump in 2023 (Fig. 1a).

54 Large increases in SST, which locally manifest as marine heatwaves, can affect regional climate
55 patterns²², sea-air CO₂ fluxes²³, and substantially impact the marine environment²⁴. For example,
56 marine heatwaves in the Indian Ocean can influence monsoon wind and precipitation over India
57 affecting water and food security²⁵. They can also interact with and intensify tropical cyclones²⁶,
58 increasing their destructiveness. Biological impacts of marine heatwaves include mass die-offs of
59 invertebrates, fish, birds, and marine mammals^{27,28}, coral bleaching²⁹, declines in key species and
60 complete ecosystem restructuring^{30,31}, all of which have socio-economic consequences^{32,33}.

61

62 While record-breaking jumps in global SSTs occur when a long-term warming trend is
63 superimposed onto an exceptionally warm year due to climate variability³⁴, the record-shattering
64 jump in globally-averaged SSTs from April 2023 to March 2024 has broken previous records by a
65 substantially larger margin than previous record-breaking jumps in SSTs. The three largest
66 margins by which globally-averaged SSTs previously broke records were 0.16°C in 2015/16,
67 0.14°C in 1997/98, and 0.09°C in 2009/10. Due to the unprecedented margin in the record-
68 breaking jump in SSTs in 2023/24, this jump in SSTs came as a surprise for the public and the
69 scientific community. This event has raised questions about the likelihood of such a jump and
70 whether jumps of this size are simulated in climate models². The failure of state-of-the-art
71 climate models to reproduce events as the jump in SSTs in 2023/24 would consequently question
72 the ability of these models to assess future risks associated with anthropogenic climate change³⁵.
73 However, if climate models are able to simulate such record-shattering jumps in globally
74 averaged SSTs, they would deliver analogues to study the evolution of the ongoing event and to

75 see if temperatures decrease again or remain high. In addition, the climate models could be used
76 to identify the drivers of such record-shattering jumps in SSTs, and their consequences for other
77 parts of the climate system and the marine ecosystem.

78

79 **Return period of record-shattering SST jumps**

80

81 Here we use observation-based monthly-mean SST estimates from various data and reanalysis
82 products (NOAA OI SST V2.1¹, ERA5³⁶, HadISST³⁷, ERSST³⁸) to quantify the likelihood of the global
83 SST jump in 2023/24 and assess whether it could have occurred without anthropogenic warming.
84 Due to the relatively short observational SST record, return periods of rare extreme events, such
85 as the record-shattering jump in globally averaged SSTs observed last year, cannot be directly
86 inferred from that observational record. To quantify the likelihood of a record-shattering jump in
87 globally averaged SSTs that exceeded the last record by at least 0.25°C as in 2023/24, we
88 constructed synthetic timeseries of 100 million years using an autoregressive model of order one
89 (AR(1)) using observation-based estimates of the trend, autocorrelation and standard deviation
90 of annual globally averaged SSTs with respective uncertainties (see Methods for a detailed
91 description how these values and their uncertainties are quantified).

92

93 Based on these synthetic observation-based timeseries, the record-shattering global jump was a
94 1-in-512-year event (mean estimate) under the current long-term warming trend (1-in-205-year

95 to 1-in-1,185-year event; 95% confidence interval based on uncertainties of the observation-
96 based trend, standard deviation, and autocorrelation estimates (see Method)) (Fig. 2). This result
97 is qualitatively insensitive to the choice of autoregressive model, to the methods that are used
98 to estimate the trend, autocorrelation, and standard deviation of annual globally averaged SSTs,
99 as well as to the observation-based SST dataset that is used for the analysis (see Methods).
100 Without underlying warming, a record-shattering jump as observed in 2023/24 is practically
101 impossible. We found indeed no record-shattering jumps in our synthetic timeseries without a
102 long-term warming trend, irrespective of the variability or autocorrelation characteristics
103 (Extended Data Figure 2).

104

105 **Record-shattering SST jumps in climate models**

106

107 Having quantified an observation-based estimate of the return period of such record-shattering
108 jumps in globally averaged SSTs, we show that such jumps – exceeding the previous record by at
109 least 0.25°C - were simulated 11 times across 270 simulations from 35 different state-of-the-art
110 climate models (see Methods) between 2000 and 2040. These four decades encompass the time
111 when the record-shattering SST jump occurred in the real world (Fig. 3a, Extended Data Figure
112 1). As the 270 climate model simulations here comprise a total of 11,070 years, the likelihood for
113 a single year to experience a record-shattering global jump in SSTs as observed in 2023/24 in the
114 climate models is 0.1%, making last year’s record-shattering SST event a 1-in-1,000-year event in
115 climate models (1-in-550-year to 1-in-2,000-year event; 95% confidence interval using the

116 Pearson-Clopper confidence interval for binomial experiments; see Methods) (Fig. 3b). Although
117 the return period estimate based on climate models is approximately twice as large as the
118 observation-based estimate of the return period, it lies within the confidence interval of the
119 observation-based estimate and the confidence intervals of both estimates largely overlap. The
120 difference in the return period might be due to lower warming trends and higher
121 autocorrelations in the models compared to the observation-based estimates (see Methods).
122 However, the observation-based estimate of the return period is also highly uncertain as it is
123 difficult to estimate the real trend, variability, and autocorrelation over a short timeseries that is
124 strongly influenced by natural climate variability so that the return period of such events might
125 well be 1000 years as estimated from the models. Overall, the probability of a simulated record-
126 breaking jump in SSTs with a certain magnitude reduces with that magnitude. For example, jumps
127 that exceed 0.2°C are 6-7 times more likely than jumps exceeding 0.25°C, while jumps that exceed
128 the previous record by a larger magnitude than 0.25°C become less likely but are not impossible
129 in climate model simulations (Fig. 3b). Under high emissions scenarios, the probability of record
130 shattering events increases (Extended Data Figure 3a), in line with higher rates of warming.
131 However, under strong mitigation scenarios, the warming trend reduces in the future and there
132 are no simulated record-shattering events simulated across the model ensemble (Extended Data
133 Figure 3b).

134

135 Record-shattering global jumps in SSTs (>0.25°C) are simulated by different models with a wide
136 range of trends, autocorrelations, and variabilities. It is thus not only the so called 'hot models'³⁹

137 with high transient climate responses, like IPSL-CM6A-LR, CESM2, and CanESM5 that simulate
138 such events. Instead, models with a small transient climate response and warming trend, such as
139 GFDL-ESM2M and MIROC6, also produce these record-shattering jumps since variability and
140 autocorrelation also affect the return period, and not just the long-term trend (Extended Data
141 Figure 2). Overall, no model stands out with an unusually small or high number of extreme events
142 per number of simulated years (see Methods).

143

144 **Pattern of record-shattering SST jumps**

145

146 The record-shattering global SST anomalies observed last year (data from NOAA OI SST V2.1¹)
147 were especially pronounced in the North Atlantic, Eastern Tropical Pacific, and North Pacific (Fig.
148 4a). While all three regions (see exact definitions in the Methods) show high regional SST
149 anomalies compared to the previous 30 years, only the North Atlantic SST anomalies have broken
150 previous records. The North Atlantic SSTs in 2023/24 surpassed the previous record by 0.42°C,
151 which was 0.17°C more than the margin by which the global SSTs had surpassed the previous
152 record in the same year. In the North Pacific, SST anomalies were only once larger than in 2023/24
153 and in the Eastern Tropical Pacific, SST anomalies were only twice larger than in 2023/24. In
154 climate models, all 11 jumps in globally-averaged SSTs that are as large as that in 2023/24
155 coincide with an El-Niño event, i.e., a positive El Niño-Southern Oscillation phase of at least 1.5°C
156 in the El-Niño 3.4 index (Fig. 4b-d). As the three most recently observed record-breaking jumps
157 that broke the respective previous record in globally averaged SSTs by unprecedented margins

158 (2023/24, 2015/16, and 1997/98) also occur during positive El-Niño phase (1.3°C, 1.9°C, and 1.7°C
159 respectively), a strong El-Niño appears to be a necessary, but not sufficient condition for such an
160 event.

161

162 For the 11 simulated global record-shattering jumps in SSTs, record-breaking regional SST
163 anomalies occur 10 times in the Eastern Tropical Pacific, 7 times in the North Atlantic, and 5 times
164 in the North Pacific. The largest margin by which North Atlantic SSTs records are broken during
165 one of the 11 global record-shattering jumps in SSTs in climate models is 0.33°C, a margin that is
166 0.09°C smaller than the extraordinarily large observed margin in 2023/24. This observed jump in
167 the North Atlantic was likely caused by a high level of surface solar radiation, weak winds, tropical
168 air⁴⁰, and changes in low cloud cover¹⁵. Such large jumps in North Atlantic SSTs are identified in
169 the 11,070 model years simulated between 2000 and 2040 five times. However, coincident global
170 and regional record-shattering jumps at the observed magnitude of 2023/24 are not found in the
171 11,070 model years between 2000 and 2040. An even larger model ensemble would be necessary
172 to see if climate models can simulate the combination of a global record-shattering jump in SSTs
173 and a record-shattering jump in SSTs in the North Atlantic in 2023 and 2024. A sudden drop in
174 aerosols from shipping emissions, which has not been prescribed as input to the climate models
175 in the CMIP scenarios, might have contributed to the extremely large observed North Atlantic
176 temperature anomaly⁴¹.

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179 **SST evolution after record-shattering jumps**

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181 We now use these model simulations to understand how SST anomalies typically develop over
182 the years that follow a record-shattering jump in SSTs. In all simulations, the global SST anomalies
183 stop being record-breaking between May and October of the second year of the record SST
184 anomalies, i.e., 13 to 18 months after the beginning of the jump in globally averaged SSTs. In the
185 real world, global SSTs dropped below record levels in July 2024 (Fig. 1a), 15 months after the
186 beginning of the record-shattering jump in globally averaged SSTs. Furthermore, SST anomalies
187 in climate models return to their level before the jump (grey lines in Figure 1) between September
188 in the year after the jump in SSTs started and September in the following year in 8 of the 11
189 simulated jumps (Extended Data Figure 4). However, in 3 of the 11 events, the SST anomalies do
190 not return to pre-jump levels over the next 10 years (Extended Data Figure 4 b-d) and beyond
191 (Extended Data Figure 5), so that the global SSTs have indeed permanently risen to a higher level
192 in these simulations. However, even in these three cases, SSTs revert back to the expected long-
193 term warming trend over the course of at most 8 years and do not shift to a new higher or steeper
194 warming trajectory (Extended Data Figure 5). The three cases occur in CanESM5 and IPSL-CM6A-
195 LR, two climate models with extremely high transient climate responses⁴² outside the recently
196 assessed range⁴³ and with atmospheric warming rates from 1981 to 2014 that substantially
197 exceed the observed rate⁴². As atmospheric warming and sea surface warming are generally
198 strongly linked⁴⁴, the overly high SST warming rates facilitate continuing high levels of SST
199 anomalies after the record-shattering jump in SSTs. Given that a return to pre-jump temperatures

200 only fails to occur in these 'hot models'³⁹, it is likely that the global SST anomalies in the real
201 world will return to temperatures more typical of those before the record-shattering by
202 September 2025. If, however, observed SSTs do not return to pre-jump levels by September
203 2025, we expect SSTs to revert back towards the long-term trend within a few years (Extended
204 Data Figure 5). If this were not the case, the ongoing extreme event would not be consistent with
205 climate model simulations.

206

207 **Outlook on warming rate and climate models**

208

209 Based on long synthetic timeseries with temporal characteristics that match available
210 observations, we estimated that the observed record-shattering jump in globally averaged SSTs
211 in 2023/24 was a 1-in-a-512-year extreme event (1-in-205-year to 1-in-1,185-year event; 95%
212 confidence interval) based on current warming rates. Such a jump would not have been possible
213 without anthropogenic warming. We have further shown that climate models indeed simulate
214 such global (60°S-60°N) annual record-shattering jumps in SSTs that exceed the previous records
215 by at least 0.25°C, like the global jump in SSTs that was observed last year. Moreover, the
216 estimated return period of these events in climate models (1-in-a-1,000-year events in models)
217 is within the confidence interval of the observation-based estimate of the return period.
218 Furthermore, in these models the simulated SST anomalies drop below record levels between
219 May and September in the year after the jump in SSTs had started, consistent with the time when
220 observed globally averaged SSTs stopped being record-breaking (July 2024). Based on the

221 simulated record-shattering jumps we conclude that it is likely that SSTs will return to pre-jump
222 levels before September 2025. In the few simulations that do not simulate a return to pre-jump
223 levels, SSTs revert to the expected warming trajectory over the following years. Thus, SSTs have
224 not shifted to a higher or accelerated warming trajectory after a record-shattering SST jump in
225 the models. The ability of climate models to simulate both the magnitude of the SST jump and
226 the timing of the decline of positive SST anomalies enhances confidence in their use for future
227 studies to understand the length, intensity, and drivers of such extreme events and to quantify
228 their impact on regional weather systems and their potentially devastating consequences for
229 terrestrial and marine ecosystems, and their services.

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329

330 **Figure Legends**

331

332 **Figure 1: Record-shattering jumps in global sea surface temperatures as observed in 2023/2024**

333 **also occur in climate model simulations.** Monthly-mean sea surface temperature (SST)

334 anomalies for the largest record-shattering annual (April to March) global (60°S-60°N) SST events

335 before 2024 for **a)** observations from NOAA OI SST V2.1¹, and climate model simulations **b)** from

336 one CMIP6 simulation (CanESM5^{16,17} – r15i1p1f1), **c)** from one simulation from the GFDL-

337 ESM2M¹⁸ large ensemble¹⁹ (ensemble member 27), and **d)** from one simulation of the CESM2²⁰

338 large ensemble²¹ (ensemble member LE2-1301.019). The years of the onset of the respective

339 events are shown as blue lines, the years of the subsequent decline as orange lines, and the 30

340 preceding years as grey lines with their mean as a black dotted line. For each of the 3 climate

341 model groups (CMIP6, GFDL-ESM2M-LE, CESM2-LE), the largest record-breaking global jump in

342 SSTs before 2023 is presented. Monthly SST anomalies for all simulated record-shattering global

343 jumps in SSTs between 2000 and 2040 that are larger in magnitude than the observed global

344 jump in SSTs in 2023 and 2024 are shown in Extended Data Figure 1.

345

346 **Figure 2: The return period of record-shattering jumps in annually-averaged global sea surface**

347 **temperatures based on past observed sea surface temperatures.** Observation-based estimate

348 of the probability density of the return period of record-shattering jumps in synthetic timeseries

349 of global sea surface temperatures that break the old record by at least 0.25°C. The mean return

350 period (dashed black line), the median return period (dotted black line) and the limits of the 95%

351 confidence interval (solid black lines) are also shown (see Methods for details).

352 **Figure 3: The return period of record-breaking annual sea surface temperature events from**
353 **increases with the size of the margin by which they exceed previous records. a)** Record-breaking
354 annual (April-March) global (60°S-60°N) sea surface temperature (SST) events and the margin
355 (Δ SST) by which they exceeded previous records based on 190 climate model simulations from
356 CMIP6 (blue dots) (Extended Data Table 1), 30 members of the GFDL-ESM2M-LE^{18,19} (orange
357 dots), 50 members from the CESM2-LE^{20,21} (green dots), and SST observation-based estimates
358 from NOAA OI SST V2.1¹ (black crosses). **b)** Return periods of record-breaking events of a given
359 magnitude (binned in regular bins of 0.025°C) calculated based on their occurrence in **a)** for the
360 ensembles of CMIP6 (blue), GFDL-ESM2M (orange), and CESM2 (green). The return periods
361 indicate the return period for a record-breaking event of that magnitude and not of an event that
362 is equal or larger than the magnitude of that bin. Return periods for Δ SSTs of more than 0.275°C
363 are not simulated by the large ensembles of GFDL-ESM2M and CESM2, possibly due to their
364 relatively small sample size (1230 years between 2000 and 2040 for the GFDL-ESM2M-LE and
365 2050 years for the CESM2-LE). Observed record-breaking events, corresponding to the crosses in
366 **a)**, are shown as dotted black vertical lines.

367

368 **Figure 4: Anomalies of record-shattering jumps in sea surface temperatures in observations**
369 **and climate models are mostly localised in the equatorial Pacific, North Pacific, and North**
370 **Atlantic.** Sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies for record-shattering (record-breaking events
371 of largest magnitude before 2024) annual (April-March) global (60°S-60°N) SST events for **a)**
372 observations from NOAA OI SST V2.1¹, and the three climate model groups of Fig. 1: **b)** CMIP6

373 (CanESM5^{16,17} – r15i1p1f1), **c**) the GFDL-ESM2M-LE^{18,19} (ensemble member 27), and **d**) the
374 CESM2-LE^{20,21} (ensemble member LE2-1301.019). The anomalies are calculated based on the
375 average SSTs of the 30 years preceding the respective record-shattering event at the years
376 corresponding to those presented in Fig. 1 for the member of the respective climate model group.

377 **Methods**

378

379 **Observations**

380 Observed SST anomalies were calculated using the global and highly-resolved NOAA OI SST V2.1¹
381 product, which is based on observations from satellites, ships, buoys, and ARGO floats. Among
382 the different available SST products⁴⁵, we have chosen NOAA OI SST V2.1¹ as it has shown the
383 best performance⁴⁵. In addition, NOAA OI SST V2.1¹ is also the only dataset that includes the
384 observations from the ARGO program that was started in 1999 and operates between 3,000 and
385 4,000 ARGO floats since 2007. Monthly NOAA OI SST V2.1¹ observation-based estimates from
386 1982 to November 2024 were downloaded (last access on 4th December 2024). Although this
387 dataset is used in the main manuscript, the underlying warming trend, the magnitude by which
388 the record-shattering jump in SSTs in 2023/24 broke the previous SST record, and the return
389 period of such record-shattering jumps in SST are also quantified for comparison using the SST
390 Analysis production version 3.0 from the European Space Agency Sea Surface Temperature
391 Climate Change Initiative based on the OSTIA reanalysis system ICDR3.0⁴⁶. This dataset is also
392 among the better performing observation-based SST estimates with a high spatial resolution⁴⁵
393 and covers the years from 1980 to 2024. In addition, longer observation-based SST timeseries
394 from one reanalysis product (ERA5³⁶) and two interpolated observational products (HadISST³⁷,
395 and ERSST³⁸) from 1940 to 2023, the years that are covered by all three SST products, are used
396 to estimate the variance and the autocorrelation of the natural temperature variability of
397 annually and globally averaged SSTs. The autocorrelation and variability are both necessary to
398 construct the synthetic timeseries that are used to estimate the return period of record-

399 shattering sea surface temperature jumps (see section ‘Observation-based estimate of the return
400 period of record-shattering sea surface temperature jumps’ below).

401

402 Here we chose to calculate annual averages starting in April as this is the month when SSTs
403 started to break records by a larger margin (Figure 1a). However, differences to previous records
404 in NOAA OI SST V2.1¹ are up to 0.009°C larger when averaging from May to April, June to May,
405 and July to June, and become smaller afterwards. The number of times that such events occur in
406 climate models varies between 11 and 12 when the first month over which one calculates the
407 annual average is between April and July. The results are hence similar for averaging periods
408 starting later in the year.

409

410 **Observation-based estimate of the return period of record-shattering sea surface temperature** 411 **jumps**

412 To estimate an observation-based estimate and the associated uncertainties of the return period
413 of record shattering SST events that breaks the previous record by the margin of 2023/24,
414 synthetic timeseries of lengths of 100 million years were constructed. These timeseries were
415 obtained using an autoregressive model of first order (AR(1)), which relies on a warming trend,
416 temperature variability (expressed as the standard deviation), and the lag-one year
417 autocorrelation.

418

419 The underlying warming trend in SSTs in 2023/24 was estimated using an Enting spline⁴⁷ that is
420 fitted to the observation-based globally and annually averaged SSTs from 1982/83 to 2023/24.
421 From this spline fit, the trend in 2023/24 was calculated as the slope of that spline fit in 2023/24.
422 The Enting spline filters short-term variability from timeseries with noise. The amount of noise
423 that is removed depends on the cut-off period, with low cut-off periods removing only the short-
424 time variability and large cut-off periods removing both the short-term and longer-term
425 variability. To determine the cut-off period that allows a robust estimate of the trend in 2023/24,
426 the trend in the 11 climate simulations that include a record-shattering jump in SSTs was
427 calculated for cut-off periods ranging from 25 to 55 years. Cut-off periods below 25 years do not
428 filter the decadal variability, and cut-off periods of 55 years are too rigid to capture non-linear
429 components⁴⁷ of long-term warming trends. In each simulation with a record-shattering jump,
430 the Enting spline was fitted to the year of the jump and the 41 years before. The length of 42
431 years was chosen as NOAA OI SST V2.1¹ also covers 42 years. The so-estimated trend was then
432 compared to the ‘true’ underlying trend. This ‘true’ trend was estimated with a 31-year running
433 mean that can be calculated for the jump years in models because the SSTs after the jump are
434 also simulated by the models. An Enting spline with a cut-off period of 40 years fits that
435 underlying ‘true’ trend best and is only $1\pm 18\%$ larger, i.e., $0.003\pm 0.049^\circ\text{C}$ per decade). With this
436 approach applied to NOAA OI SST V2.1¹, we estimate the trend in 2023/24 to be 0.269°C per
437 decade. The uncertainty of the estimated trend was quantified using the synthetic timeseries of
438 100 million years with a trend of 0.269°C per decade and the best estimate of the variance and
439 autocorrelation (see paragraph below). At each of the around 225,000 record-shattering jumps
440 in this timeseries, the trend was estimated with an Enting spline with a cut-off period of 40 years.

441 The standard deviation of these estimated trends is 0.037°C per decade. Thus, the estimated
442 trend from the Enting spline has a likelihood of 95% to be between 0.195 and 0.343°C per decade.

443

444 To further quantify the sensitivity of the resulting trend to the estimation method, we fitted a
445 linear trend from 2004/2005 to 2023/24 to approximate the trend in the year of the jump in
446 NOAA OI SST V2.1¹. The slope of this linear fit is 0.254°C per decade, slightly smaller than the
447 estimate from the Enting spline ($0.269 \pm 0.037^{\circ}\text{C}$ per decade) as it does not capture the slight non-
448 linear warming component⁴² but well within the uncertainty range. These sensitivity tests
449 highlight that the largest uncertainty of the trend estimates results from the climate variability
450 that is superimposed on the underlying trend and not from the method that is used to determine
451 the trend.

452

453 As opposed to the estimate of the trend, we could not rely on observation-based SST data over
454 the satellite period, like NOAA OI SST V2.1¹, for the estimation of autocorrelation and variance,
455 as the relatively short length of the satellite period (1982 until today) makes uncertainties of the
456 autocorrelation and variance large. Instead, the observation-based variance and lag-one
457 autocorrelation are estimated from the three SST reanalysis products described above over the
458 period 1940-2023 after detrending the data using a cubic spline, resulting in three estimates
459 each. As it is not evident which product performs best, the mean of all three estimates is used as
460 the most likely estimate of the autocorrelation and variability. An implicit assumption for the
461 estimation of the autocorrelation and variance is that the temperature variability follows a

462 Gaussian distribution (Extended Data Figure 6). For the ERA5³⁶, HadISST³⁷, and ERSST³⁸ products,
463 three tests (Kolmogorov Smirnov, Shapiro-Wilk, and Anderson-Darling) were employed to test
464 whether the SST anomalies follow a Gaussian distribution. Across these three tests and three
465 timeseries the p-values vary from 0.26 to 0.90 indicating no significant deviation from a Gaussian
466 distribution. We thus conclude that the SST data is well modelled by a Gaussian distribution.

467

468 To estimate the uncertainty of the autocorrelation and variance, sampling distributions for the
469 best estimates of the variance and autocorrelation are constructed. For normally distributed time
470 series of a given length, theoretical sampling distributions of variance and autocorrelation
471 estimates are known^{49,50}. These sampling distributions characterize the dispersion of estimates
472 around a true value. The variance of the sampling distribution thus informs about the uncertainty
473 in the estimate from internal climate variability for an estimate from a single product. As the best
474 estimates of the variance and autocorrelation are both an average of three products, the
475 uncertainty is smaller than the uncertainty from a single product. To reflect this reduced
476 uncertainty, we randomly sample 10,000 times three values from the respective distribution and
477 average over these three values. The resulting values are then the sampling distribution of the
478 average estimate of the three products. The resulting uncertainties are relatively large (Extended
479 Data Figure 7b, c) as the internal climate variability still renders the estimation of the actual
480 variability and autocorrelation uncertain in a timeseries that covers 84 years from 1940 to 2023.
481 These large uncertainties due to the internal variability cover the individual estimates from the
482 three products (Extended Data Figure 7). Furthermore, the sensitivity tests towards the

483 detrending method were evaluated. When using a 2nd order polynomial or an Enting spline with
484 a cut-off period of 40 years, the results change by $\pm 10\%$ and are within the large uncertainties in
485 the estimates resulting from the internal climate variability.

486

487 We then constructed 10,000 AR(1) models by randomly sampling 10,000 combinations of trends,
488 autocorrelations, and variability from the distributions of the respective quantities (see
489 histograms in Extended Data Figure 7). From these 10,000 AR(1) models, a distribution of
490 observational return periods was estimated, with its spread representing the uncertainty in the
491 return period estimate. The resulting mean and median of the return period are 512 years and
492 448 years, respectively, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 205 to 1,185 years. The
493 lower bound of the confidence interval is the return period for which 2.5% of probability mass is
494 distributed over lower return periods. Consistently, the upper bound is defined such that lower
495 return periods have 97.5% of the probability mass.

496

497 To test the sensitivity to the choice of the observation-based SST estimate, the underlying
498 warming trend, the magnitude by which the record-shattering jump in SSTs in 2023/24 broke the
499 previous SST record, and the return period of such record-shattering jumps in SST was also
500 quantified using the SST Analysis production version 3.0 from the European Space Agency Sea
501 Surface Temperature Climate Change Initiative based on the OSTIA reanalysis system ICDR3.0⁴⁶.
502 In that dataset, the SST jump in 2023/24 is 0.23°C, the underlying trend in 2023/24 is 0.209°C.
503 per decade, and the resulting return period estimate is 543 years with a 95% confidence interval

504 of 204 to 1,371 years. Thus, the return period is almost the same as the return period estimated
505 based on NOAA OI SST V2.1¹. Furthermore, the number of record-shattering events in climate
506 models for a jump of 0.23°C is 19, resulting in a return period of 583 years. Thus, the estimates
507 of the return period of record-shattering events based on observations and models are closer
508 when using this dataset instead of NOAA OI SST V2.1¹.

509

510 The sensitivity of the return period estimate to the choice of the underlying statistical model was
511 also tested. In addition to using the AR(1) model, the return period was calculated with an
512 autoregressive model of order 2 (AR(2) model) and a moving average of order 1 model (MA(1)
513 model). The resulting mean return periods are 484 years (196-1,142 years, 95% confidence
514 interval) for the AR(2) model and 498 years (201-1,179 years) for the MA(1) model. As the results
515 are almost indistinguishable from the results with the AR(1) model that resulted in a return
516 period of 512 (205-1,185), we here rely on the well-established AR(1) model.

517

518 In addition to these 10,000 timeseries, a smaller number of timeseries was constructed for a
519 range of combinations of autocorrelations, standard deviations, and trends to visualize the
520 respective effect of the effect of each quantity on the resulting return period of record-shattering
521 jumps in SSTs and to be able to compare the models to observation-based estimates in terms of
522 autocorrelations, standard deviations, trends, and return periods (Extended Data Figure 2).

523

524 **Climate model simulations**

525 We use 270 simulations from 35 coupled climate models: 170 simulations are from CMIP6
526 (Extended Data Table 1), 30 simulations are from the GFDL-ESM2M¹⁸ large ensemble from the
527 University of Bern¹⁹ (ensemble members are numbered 1 to 30), and 50 simulations are from the
528 CESM2²⁰ large ensemble²¹ (ensemble members 51 to 100). Although the CESM2-LE contains 100
529 ensemble members, only the second half of the members was used, as the first half of the
530 members had too high temperature variability due to too high sensitivities of aerosol-cloud
531 interactions to variability in biomass burning⁴⁸.

532

533 The CMIP6 and CESM2-LE simulations are forced with historical data from CMIP6 until 2014 and
534 with the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) 5-8.5 (CMIP6 simulations) and 3-7.0 (CESM2-
535 LE)⁵¹. The GFDL-ESM2M-LE simulations are forced with historical data from CMIP5 until 2005 and
536 with RCP8.5 afterwards⁵². The resulting radiative forcing between SSP3-7.0, SSP5-8.5, and RCP8.5
537 is smaller than 3% in 2020, smaller than 5% in 2030, and smaller than 7% in 2040^{53,54} resulting in
538 global warming that is statistically indistinguishable until 2040³⁵.

539

540 To compare the climate models to the observed record-shattering jumps in globally averaged
541 SSTs over 2023/24, annual SST means were calculated from April to March, the part of the year
542 when the observed record-shattering jump occurred in 2023/24. For each model, monthly data

543 from each model's original grid was analysed to avoid introducing errors by regriding the data
544 first.

545

546 The climate model return period for record-breaking global jumps in SST that exceed the previous
547 record by at least 0.25°C is estimated by counting the number of record-breaking jumps in SST
548 simulations between 2000 and 2040, the years when the trend is approximately similar to the
549 trend in 2023/24. For the climate model return period estimate, a confidence interval for the
550 return period estimate of record-breaking global jumps in SST was constructed by identifying the
551 counted number of such events in the model simulations (here 11) with the outcome of a
552 binomial experiment⁵⁵. The binomial parameter p represents the probability of any year in any
553 model simulation to show such an event. We then calculate the 95% Pearson-Clopper confidence
554 interval ($p_{\text{lower}}, p_{\text{upper}}$) for the binomial parameter p ^{55,56}. As the return period is given by $1 / p$, the
555 confidence interval of the return period is $(1 / p_{\text{upper}}, 1 / p_{\text{lower}})$. Here, the confidence interval of
556 the return period is 550-2,000 years. The Pearson-Clopper confidence interval was chosen over
557 that assuming a normal distribution for p , since p is close to zero where normality cannot be
558 assumed⁵³. Nonetheless, a relatively similar confidence interval (633-2,459 years) would be
559 estimated when assuming a normal distribution. This similar result suggests that the confidence
560 interval is relatively insensitive to the chosen approach.

561

562 We have not detected an unusual proportion of record-shattering SST jumps in any of the model
563 ensembles. Therefore, most record-shattering jumps in SSTs are found in model simulations that

564 tend to have the largest number of ensemble members (2 such events in 30 GFDL-ESM2M-LE
565 members, 2 in 50 CESM2-LE members, 2 in 50 CanESM5 members, 4 in 43 MIROC6 members,
566 and 1 in 6 IPSL-CM6A-LR members). Given that the observation-based estimate of the return of
567 record-shattering jumps in SSTs has a confidence interval between a 1-in-a-205-year event and a
568 1-in-a-1,185-year event, it appears plausible that no such events are sampled in model ensembles
569 with 10 or less ensemble members, which cover a maximum of 410 years. The smallest ensemble
570 in which an event was simulated was IPSL-CM6A-LR, which runs over 246 years. Finding such an
571 event in one small ensemble is also plausible given that there are many such small ensembles
572 without a record-shattering SST jump. Lastly, the most events were found in the MIROC6
573 ensemble with 4 events in 1,763 years (43 ensemble members). This corresponds to a return
574 period of around 440 years, within the uncertainty range of the observation-based estimate.

575

576 The climate model simulations analysed here have temperature trends, temperature variabilities
577 and autocorrelations that spread around the observation-based estimates of these three
578 variables (Extended Data Figure 2). To compare the trends, temperature variabilities and
579 autocorrelations in the models to the observation-based estimates, we estimated the quantities
580 in the same way as we did for the observation-based estimates. The multi-model mean
581 temperature trend in 2023/24 in the models is 19% smaller (43% smaller to 9% larger,
582 interquartile range) than the observation-based trend estimated from NOAA OI SST V2.1¹ (0.27°C
583 per decade) in CMIP6 model simulations, 26% smaller (11-44% smaller) than the observation-
584 based trend in CESM2 simulations, and 37% smaller (25-50% smaller) in GFDL-ESM2M

585 simulations. The multi-model mean standard deviation of the temperature variability
586 (temperature from 1940 to 2023 after being detrended with a 3rd order polynomial) is 16%
587 higher (3% smaller to 40% larger) in CMIP6 model simulations than the average of the
588 observation-based estimates based on ERA5³⁶ (0.085°C), HadISST³⁷ (0.082°C), and ERSST³⁸
589 (0.092°C), and 15% (10-21%) and 20% (14-26%) higher than the observation-based estimate in
590 CESM2 and GFDL-ESM2M simulations, in line with the overestimation of decadal trends of major
591 climate modes in CMIP6 models⁵⁷. In addition, the multi-model mean autocorrelation is 55% (31-
592 86%) larger in CMIP6 models than the average of the observation-based estimates based on
593 ERA5³⁶ (0.20), HadISST³⁷ (0.31), and ERSST³⁸ (0.41), 23% (8-38%) larger in CESM2 simulations, and
594 19% (8-37%) larger in GFDL-ESM2M simulations. A part of the difference between the models'
595 and the observed parameter estimates may be due to the uncertainty in the observed estimates
596 (standard deviations for the parameter estimates of SST trend, SST standard deviation, and year-
597 to-year SST autocorrelation of 0.03 °C dec⁻¹, 0.004 °C, and 0.06, respectively). In addition, the
598 counting of the record-shattering jumps in globally averaged SSTs led to a return period of 1,000
599 years, higher than the observation-based estimate of the return period (512 years) but within the
600 confidence interval (205 to 1,185 years). The slightly higher simulated return period might well
601 be the result of the slight tendency towards relatively high autocorrelations and relatively small
602 trends, compensated by a relatively high standard deviation. However, the observation-based
603 estimates of the return period might also just be affected by the internal variability leading to a
604 too low best guess based on observations.

605

606 Regionally averaged timeseries

607 Timeseries of spatially averaged SST anomalies were calculated for four different regions: 60°S
608 to 60°N, the El-Niño 3.4 index region in the Eastern Tropical Pacific from 5°S to 5°N and from
609 170°W to 120°W, the North Atlantic as defined by all Atlantic open-ocean biomes as defined by
610 Fay and McKinley (2014)⁵⁸ excluding the Mediterranean Sea and limited by 0°N, and the North
611 Pacific as defined by the North Pacific subpolar seasonally stratified biome and the subtropical
612 seasonally stratified biome from Fay and McKinley (2014)⁵⁸. The mask for the respective biomes
613 were mapped on each individual native model grid.

614

615 Data availability

616 The Earth system model output used in this study is available via the Earth System Grid
617 Federation (<https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/projects/cmip6-dkrz/>). The large ensemble from CESM2 is
618 here available: <https://www.earthsystemgrid.org/dataset/ucar.cgd.cesm2le.output.html>. The
619 monthly 2-D sea surface temperature output from the GFDL-ESM2M large ensemble is here
620 available: <https://www.seanoe.org/data/00897/100853/>. The NOAA OI SST V2.1¹ data is
621 available here: <https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.noaa.oisst.v2.highres.html>. The SST
622 Analysis production version 3.0 from the European Space Agency Sea Surface Temperature
623 Climate Change Initiative based on the OSTIA reanalysis system ICDR3.0³⁷ is available here:
624 <https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/4a9654136a7148e39b7feb56f8bb02d2/>. The ERA5 sea
625 surface temperature data is available here:
626 <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-single-levels-monthly->

627 [means?tab=overview](#), the ERSST sea surface temperatures are available here:
628 <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/extended-reconstructed-sst>, and the HadISST sea surface
629 temperatures are available here:
630 <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadisst/data/download.html>. All maps were created
631 using the Basemap tool in Python (<https://matplotlib.org/basemap/stable/>).

632

633 **Code availability**

634 The code that was used for this study is available under <https://zenodo.org/records/14618176>⁸³.

635

636

637

638 **References - Methods and Extended Data**

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729

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743

744 **Author contributions**

745 This idea for the study was conceived by JT. A detailed outline was developed by JT in
746 collaboration with TLF and TFS. JT performed the model output analysis and produced the figures.
747 FAB built the statistical models for the observations-based estimate of the return period of the
748 jump in SSTs. The CMIP6 sea surface temperature timeseries (60°S-60°N, El-Niño index 3.4, North
749 Pacific, and North Atlantic) were provided by LV, and the timeseries for the same regions from
750 the large ensembles of CESM2 and GFDL-ESM2M by JT. The GFDL ESM2M-LE simulations were

751 conducted by FAB with guidance by TLF. The initial manuscript was written by JT. All authors
752 contributed ideas, discussed the results and wrote the manuscript.

753

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756 be addressed to JT (jens.terhaar@unibe.ch).

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759 **Extended Data Table and Figure legends**

760

761 **Extended Data Table 1. List of CMIP6 climate models and the number of ensemble members**
762 **per model used in this study.**

763

764 **Extended Data Figure 1: Record-shattering jumps in global sea surface temperature as**
765 **observed in 2023/24 are simulated by 11 climate models between 2000 and 2040.** Sea surface
766 temperature (SST) climatologies for record-shattering (record-breaking events of largest
767 magnitude before 2024) annual (April-March) global (60°S-60°N) SST events for **a)** observations
768 from NOAA OI SST V2.1¹, and climate model simulations from **b)-h)** CMIP6 (CanESM5^{16,17} –
769 r14i1p1f1, CanESM5^{16,17} – r15i1p1f1, IPSL-CM6A-LR⁷⁶ - r14i1p1f1, MIROC6⁷⁷ – r3i1p1f1,
770 MIROC6⁷⁷ – r22i1p1f1, MIROC6⁷⁷ – r25i1p1f1, MIROC6⁷⁷ – r39i1p1f1), **i)-j)** the GFDL-ESM2M-
771 LE^{18,19} (ensemble members 3 and 27), and **k) – l)** the CESM2-LE^{20,21} (ensemble members LE2-
772 1301.002 and LE2-1251.017). The years of the onset of the respective events are shown as blue
773 lines, the years of the decline as orange lines, and the 30 preceding years as grey lines with a
774 black dotted line showing the average of these preceding 30 years.

775

776 **Extended Data Figure 2: The return period of record-shattering jumps in sea surface**
777 **temperature depends sensitively on the warming trend, and the autocorrelation and variance**
778 **of annual sea surface temperatures.** The return period of record-shattering sea surface

779 temperature (SST) events, defined as events when the annually averaged SST (April to March)
780 between 60°S and 60°N is at least 0.25°C (record-breaking SST observed in 2023/2024) larger
781 than the previous record SST, is plotted in dependence of the warming trend over a given period
782 and the temperature variability for five different autocorrelations: **a)** 0.2, **b)** 0.3, **c)** 0.4, **d)** 0.5,
783 and **e)** 0.6. The return period is calculated based on timeseries of 100 million years with an AR(1)
784 model and prescribed trends, variability and autocorrelation (see methods). The dots indicate
785 each simulation, and their location indicates the trends, variability and autocorrelation derived
786 from these simulations. The larger dots show the simulations that included a record-shattering
787 jump in SSTs. Accordingly, the crosses indicate the trend from NOAA OI SST V2.1¹ and variability
788 and autocorrelation from ERA5³⁶ (cross in **b)**), HadISST³⁷ (cross in **c)**), and ERSST³⁸ (cross in **d)**),

789

790 **Extended Data Figure 3: The return period of record-breaking annual sea surface temperature**
791 **events over the 21st century depends sensitively on the emission scenario.** Record-breaking
792 annual (April-March) global (60°S-60°N) sea surface temperature (SST) events based on 190
793 climate model simulations from CMIP6 (blue dots) (Extended Data Table 1) for **a)** the high-
794 emission SSP5-8.5 and **b)** the low-emission SSP1-2.6. In addition, record-breaking SST events
795 based on SST observation-based estimates from NOAA OI SST V2.1¹ are shown as black crosses.

796

797 **Extended Data Figure 4: In all simulated record-shattering jumps, sea surface temperatures**
798 **anomalies are mostly localised in the equatorial Pacific, North Pacific, and North Atlantic.** Sea
799 surface temperature (SST) climatologies for record-shattering (record-breaking events of largest
800 magnitude before 2024) annual (April-March) global (60°S-60°N) SST events for **a)** observations

801 from NOAA OI SST V2.1¹, and climate model simulations from **b)-h)** CMIP6 (CanESM5^{16,17} –
802 r14i1p1f1, CanESM5^{16,17} – r15i1p1f1, IPSL-CM6A-LR⁷⁶ - r14i1p1f1, MIROC6⁷⁷ – r3i1p1f1,
803 MIROC6⁷⁷ – r22i1p1f1, MIROC6⁷⁷ – r25i1p1f1, MIROC6⁷⁷ – r39i1p1f1), **i)-j)** the GFDL-ESM2M-
804 LE^{18,19} (ensemble members 3 and 27), and **k) – l)** the CESM2-LE^{20,21} (ensemble members LE2-
805 1301.002 and LE2-1251.017) between 2000 and 2040. The years of the onset of the respective
806 events are shown as blue lines, the years of the decline as orange lines, the 10 years following
807 the event as green lines, and the 30 preceding years (pre-jump years) as grey lines with a black
808 dotted line showing the average of these preceding 30 years.

809

810 **Extended Data Figure 5: Annual global sea surface temperature anomalies return to the long-**
811 **term warming trend after record-shattering jumps in sea surface temperatures that exceed**
812 **previous records by more than 0.25°C.** Annual (April-March) global (60°S-60°N) sea surface
813 temperature (SST) for the 71 years around a record-shattering jump in SSTs that exceeds the
814 previous record by at least 0.25°C for the simulations **a)** CanESM5^{16,17} – r14i1p1f1, **b)**
815 CanESM5^{16,17} – r15i1p1f1, and **c)** IPSL-CM6A-LR⁷⁶ – r14i1p1f1, the simulations in which SSTs do
816 not come back to pre-jump levels in the future (blue lines). The respective ensemble means for
817 CanESM^{16,17} (50 ensemble members) and IPSL-CM6A-LR⁷⁶ (6 ensemble members) are shown in
818 comparison (orange lines). The year of the jump in SSTs is shown as a dashed black line.

819

820 **Extended Data Figure 6: Observation-based sea surface temperature anomalies follow a**
821 **gaussian distribution.** Distribution of global (60°-60°N) annual (April to March) Sea surface
822 temperature (SST) anomalies for the observation-based reanalysis product ERA5³⁶ from 1940 to

823 2023 (blue line). After detrending (see Methods), the anomalies were binned in 21 bins of 0.025°C
824 each. In addition, a gaussian distribution with the standard deviation of the SST anomalies is
825 shown.

826

827 **Extended Data Figure 7: Sampling distributions for the 3-product averages of variance and**
828 **autocorrelation and of the single trend estimate.** The single estimate for the trend is shown as
829 a dashed line in **a)** and the three different estimates are shown as dashed orange (ERA5³⁶), dotted
830 green (HadISST³⁷), and dash-dotted purple (ERSST³⁸) lines in **b)** and **c)** together with the mean
831 estimate of the three individual estimates as a solid black line.

832

a

NOAA OI SST V2.1 (2023-2024)

b

CMIP6 (CanESM5 - r15i1p1f1) (2020-2021)

c

GFDL-ESM2M-LE (ensemble member 27) (2003-2004)

d

CESM2-LE (LE2-1301.019) (2016-2017)

Climate model	Ensemble members	Reference
ACCESS-CM2	3	59
ACCESS-ESM1-5	10	60
BCC-CSM2-MR	1	61
CanESM5-CanOE	3	16,17
CanESM5	50	16,17
CESM2	3	20
CESM2-WACCM	1	20
CIesm	1	62
CMCC-CM2-SR5	1	63
CMCC-ESM2	1	64
CNRM-CM6-1-HR	1	65
CNRM-CM6-1	6	65
CNRM-ESM2-1	4	66
EC-Earth3	2	67
EC-Earth3-Veg-LR	3	67
EC-Earth3-Veg	5	67
FGOALS-f3-L	3	68
FGOALS-g3	4	69
FIO-ESM-2-0	3	70
GFDL-ESM4	1	71
GISS-E2-1-G	7	72
HadGEM3-GC31-LL	1	73
HadGEM3-GC31-MM	1	73
INM-CM4-8	1	74
INM-CM5-0	1	75
IPSL-CM6A-LR	6	76
MCM-UA-1-0	1	unknown
MIROC6	43	77
MIROC-ES2L	6	78
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	2	79
MPI-ESM1-2-LR	10	80
MRI-ESM2-0	1	81
NorESM2-LM	1	82
NorESM2-MM	1	82

a

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